

lings (27-34 cm height) remained completely under water for nearly a week, whereas the top 2-3 leaves of fertilized seedlings were above water. The second flood killed most of the unfertilized seedlings. The mean grain yields of all rice varieties were similar, but crops raised from vegetative tillers

yielded best. Panicle number in the vegetative propagated crop was 112-132 m⁻² and their weight was 3.39-3.63 g, leading to a grain yield of more than 4 t ha⁻¹. Nursery seedlings had very low yields and poor crop stand even with good panicle weight (2.70-3.32 g) because the flood reduced panicle num-

ber (61-88%) and tillers. Straw yield was highest with Matangini, and its nursery seedlings were also significantly better than those of Utkalprabha and Gayatri.

Seedling height and dry weight at transplanting determine survivability, crop stand, and productivity under flood-prone conditions. Suitable varieties can be obtained either by uprooting vegetative tillers from a field-grown crop or from a conventional nursery seedbed raised using relatively low seed density and basal N fertilization. ■

Effect of seedling vigor on growth and yield attributes of rice varieties under flood-prone conditions. Cuttack, India. 1993.

Treatment	Seedling vigor ^a		Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)
	Height (cm)	Dry weight (g seedling ⁻¹)					
Gayatri (semidwarf)							
Unfertilized seedlings	27	0.08	74	15	2.89	0.2	0.3
Fertilized seedlings	33	0.15	93	28	3.30	0.9	1.5
Vegetative tillers	71	0.86	106	124	3.63	4.1	5.5
Utkalprabha (semi-tall)							
Unfertilized seedlings	32	0.08	105	22	3.18	0.4	0.8
Fertilized seedlings	56	0.18	107	34	3.32	0.7	1.5
Vegetative tillers	71	0.79	136	133	3.59	4.3	6.2
Matangini (tall)							
Unfertilized seedlings	34	0.17	107	31	2.70	0.7	1.4
Fertilized seedlings	57	0.22	114	43	2.98	1.3	2.3
Vegetative tillers	98	1.25	164	112	3.39	4.1	7.6
CD (0.05)							
Varieties			6	ns	0.18	ns	0.35
Kind of seedlings			6	8	0.18	0.33	0.35
Varieties × kind of seedlings			6	13	ns	ns	0.61
CV (%)			3.2	12.9	5.5	17.7	11.6

^aBased on mean of 25 seedlings.

Water depth (cm)

Flooding patterns during the growth period of rice. Cuttack, India. 1993.

Integrated pest management

A survey of rice constraints in the Mekong Delta

P. V. Du, Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute, Can Tho, Vietnam; S. Savary, IRRI-ORSTOM Joint Project on Rice Pest Characterization; and F. A. Elazegui, IRRI

A survey was conducted in three rice-cropping seasons of 1996 in the Can Tho Province of Vietnam. The sample consisted of 73 fields distributed over these successive seasons (20, 32, and 21 fields) and four villages. The Survey Portfolio of the Rice Research Prioritization Project supported by the Rockefeller Foundation was used.

Analysis of variance was carried out on individual injuries attributable to

pests for the three seasons (see table). Leaf folder (LF), deadhearts (DH), and leaf blast (LB) injuries were higher in winter-spring; weed infestation (above the rice crop canopy WA) and sheath rot (ShR) injuries were higher in summer; and brown spot (BS) and bacterial blight (BLB) injuries were higher in autumn. Brown planthopper (BPH) populations were higher in winter-spring, although remaining at low levels. Injury due to red stripe syndrome (RS) was also highest in winter-spring, and next highest in summer.

Analysis of variance was likewise conducted on individual injuries for various levels of cropping practices. We found numerical, but not significant effects, of fertilizer inputs on levels of

injuries, except for sheath blight (ShB) ($P < 0.01$, increase with fertilizer application) and weed infestation below the rice crop (WB, $P = 0.02$, decrease with fertilizer application). No numerical trends, nor significant differences, were found to suggest a link between fertilizer input and BS or RS. Some injuries differed ($P < 0.05$) in intensity depending on location (village): WB, DH, BS, and NB, reflecting the influence of a number of possible factors (e.g., soil characteristics, varieties, crop husbandry). No significant insecticide effects on any injury attributable to insects were found except one, BPH, where injury was significantly ($P = 0.039$) increased when insecticide was used. No significant effect of fungicide on

any injury attributable to pathogens was found either, except for ShB, whose injury was also increased by fungicide use. Relationships between different cropping practices (e.g., water management, variety, etc.) did not show a distinctive pattern. A multivariate approach was then used to address multiple, complex associations.

Results of chi square tests and multiple correspondence analysis can be summarized as follows:

Winter-spring was characterized by higher levels of LB, RS, and BPH; summer by higher RS and WA; and autumn by higher BLB and BS, but lower levels of RS. ShB injury, high in all seasons, peaked in winter-spring.

In winter-spring, water management was generally good; in summer, water stress was found in some fields, and there were low fertilizer inputs and higher use of herbicides; in autumn, water excess (floods) occurred in some fields.

Winter-spring was characterized by higher yields (5 t ha⁻¹ and more), summer by medium yields (2.5-5 t ha⁻¹, and autumn by low yields (2.5 t ha⁻¹ and less).

Multiple correspondence analysis using patterns of cropping practices and injury variables described much of the yield variation: at least 88% of each yield class is accounted for on the first two

Variation in levels of injuries with rice cropping seasons. Can Tho Province, Mekong Delta. 1996.

Injury ^a	Winter-spring (Dec-Mar)	Summer (Apr-Jul)	Autumn (Jul-Oct)	F	P
Leafhopper ^b	517	118	9	32.2	<0.001
Whiteheads ^c	0.19	0.38	0.51	0.80	0.45
Deadhearts ^c	2.50	1.00	0.90	4.69	0.01
Weed below the rice canopy ^d	170	400	414	2.74	0.07
Weed above the rice canopy ^d	385	600	232	4.56	0.01
Neck blast ^c	2.83	1.17	0.36	1.98	0.14
Stem rot ^c	0.75	0.21	0.12	2.72	0.07
Sheath rot ^c	0.77	7.41	1.84	4.96	0.01
Sheath blight ^c	3.28	4.07	9.22	3.32	0.04
Red stripe ^b	352	228	135	4.67	0.01
Brown spot ^b	649	583	1885	17.3	<0.001
Leaf blast ^b	253	5	3	18.0	<0.001
Bacterial blight ^b	21	16	195	4.38	0.01
Rice bugs ^e	0.35	0.33	3.08	2.58	0.08
Brown planthopper ^e	75	28	10	9.70	<0.001

^aInjury levels are indicated in different units. The magnitude of entries does not reflect the magnitude of the injurious effect on the crop and the yield-reducing effects. ^bArea under progress curve of mean proportion of injured leaves. ^cMaximum proportion of tillers injured over four successive visits. ^dArea under progress curve of proportion of soil covered by weed canopy. ^eArea under progress curve of mean insect catches over four successive visits.

combined axes. (These axes represent independent combinations of variables, except yield, using a chi-square distance.)

This analysis indicates no apparent effect of pesticide use—fungicides, insecticides, and herbicides—on the pattern of distribution of injuries. In other words, pesticides do not appear to have any significant effect on the overall occurrence of pests, except for the two cases mentioned.

This survey provides a first overview of injuries due to pests in Mekong Delta rice cultivation. It points to sea-

sonal patterns, a few environmental factors that may influence injuries, and some links among injuries. The survey results permit us to make hypotheses, especially to explain why pesticide use, which is very high, has so little effect on injury levels, and hypotheses about red stripe syndrome. Surveys in the Mekong Delta are ongoing. We expect to derive from an additional year of survey—and a larger survey data set—production situations (combination of climatic and crop management practices) that will permit us to develop testable hypotheses. ■

Integrated pest management—insects

Impact of methyl parathion on the natural enemies of rice insect pests in Cambodia

G. S. Arida, K. L. Heong, IRRI; P. Visarto and H. J. Nesbitt, Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project

Methyl parathion is one of the most commonly used insecticides in Cambodia. An experiment at Kap Srau Station, Phnom Penh, during 1994 main crop season evaluated methyl parathion effects on major arthropod groups in rainfed lowland rice.

We planted IR72 in a randomized complete block design on 35- × 20-m plots, with treatments of sprayed and unsprayed plots each replicated three times. Methyl parathion was sprayed 14 and 38 d after transplanting (DT) at 0.75 kg ai ha⁻¹. Arthropods were sampled 1 d before (DBS) and at 3 d after spraying (DAS). Samples were taken from 10 randomly selected sites per plot using a blower-vac suction machine. Each sample site was enclosed with a bottomless plastic bucket fixed with a muslin cloth around its

opening to prevent escape of arthropods during suction. The enclosed area was 0.102 m² and covered 3-4 hills. Arthropods were placed in labeled vials with 80% alcohol, counted, and identified. Damage from defoliators was also recorded at 45 DT from 10 randomly selected hills plot⁻¹. Yields were taken from 2- × 5-m area in each plot and adjusted to 14% moisture content.

The arthropod population collected at the first set of samplings was too low for useful comparisons. In the second sampling, green leafhopper density